

Linnæus University

Monthly Report April 2026 SENTINEL Wild Birds

Söderquist, P., Byrne, A., Lewis, N., van Toor, M. L., Waldenström, J., &
SENTINEL Wild Birds Consortium

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SUMMARY REPORT

1. OVERVIEW

SENTINEL Wild Birds aims to enhance the understanding of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) virus dynamics in wild bird populations by conducting active surveillance at key locations in and near Europe. These locations are divided into the following surveillance nodes: Node 1 Gulf of Finland (Finland, Estonia), Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea (Sweden, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland), Node 3 Western Black Sea (Ukraine), Node 4 Eastern Black Sea (Georgia), Node 5 Wadden Sea (the Netherlands), Node 6 Lake Constance (Germany, Austria, Switzerland), Node 7 Veneto Region (Italy), Node 8 Camargue (France), and Node 9 Gulf of Cadiz (Spain). This monthly summary provides an update on sampled wild birds as part of an early warning system to support wildlife management and disease prevention efforts. The data in this report are based on previously unpublished samples from seven nodes, collected from January to April 2026.

Note that the numbers presented in this and previous monthly reports are based on data extracts prepared at the time of analysis. As some samples may be re-analysed or reported in more than one period, the numbers reported across different monthly summaries are not strictly additive and may differ slightly from aggregated totals in the underlying dataset.

2. RESULTS

2.1 DATA COLLECTION

Since the last monthly report was published on 27th of March 2026 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19254891>), and as of 15th April 2026, test results have been submitted for 825 samples taken from 535 individuals representing 26 taxa from seven nodes in and near Europe (Table 1). Of the 825 collected samples, 278 (34%) were cloacal swabs, 275 (33%) tracheal/oropharyngeal swabs, 143 (17%) combined swabs (choana + cloacal), 102 (12%) faecal samples, 15 (2%) feather swabs, and 12 (1%) samples from multiple organs/tissues.

Prevalence and host species sampled

The most sampled species were Mallard (132 individuals) and Black-headed Gull (113 individuals; Table 1). Highest bird-level prevalence in species with a sample size of at least 30 individuals was found in Lesser Black-backed Gull (19%; n=54) and Mallard (6%, n=132). Overall bird-level prevalence was 4% (21 of 535 individuals; Table 1).

TABLE 1 Most recently sampled individuals in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Total number of individuals sampled in the wild, number of individuals tested positive for avian influenza virus as well as bird-level prevalence. The table includes previously unpublished samples from January to April 2026.

Group/species	Node 2 Latvia		Node 3 Ukraine		Node 4 Georgia		Node 5 Netherlands		Node 6 Austria		Node 6 Germany		Node 6 Switzerland		Node 7 Italy		Node 8 France		Total		
	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Prev.
<i>Waterfowl</i>																					
Mute Swan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0%
Greylag Goose	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0%
Common Shelduck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	15	0	0%
Egyptian Goose	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0%
Mallard	3	0	87	7	23	0	0	0	2	0	17	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	132	8	6%
Domestic Mallard	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0%
Northern Pintail	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0%
Eurasian Teal	0	0	2	1	1	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13	1	8%
Garganey	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0%
Common Pochard	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
Tufted Duck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
<i>Grebes</i>																					
Black-necked Grebe	0	0	2	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0%
Great Crested Grebe	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0%
<i>Cormorants</i>																					
Great Cormorant	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	32	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	35	0	0%
<i>Rails</i>																					
Eurasian Coot	0	0	29	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29	2	7%
<i>Waders</i>																					
Eurasian Oystercatcher	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0%
Ruff	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
Red Knot	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
Ruddy Turnstone	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0%
Dunlin	0	0	0	0	0	0	34	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34	0	0%
Common Redshank	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0%
Common Snipe	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
<i>Larids</i>																					
Black-headed Gull	0	0	0	0	85	0	0	0	16	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	113	0	0%
Mediterranean Gull	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
Yellow-legged Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	36	0	36	0	0%
Lesser Black-backed Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	54	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	54	10	19%
Total	3	0	121	10	144	0	103	10	81	0	29	1	3	0	15	0	36	0	535	21	4%

HPAI detection

Of all samples, 22 (3%) tested positive for avian influenza virus, of which none were confirmed as highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) virus, although three H5-positive samples have not yet been assessed for pathogenicity (Figure 1; Table 2).

Other AIV detections

Of the samples testing positive for avian influenza virus (AIV), three were subtyped with rRT-PCR as H5 viruses with undetermined NA subtypes. All three were adult Mallards (two males and one female) caught in Ukraine in late January. They have not yet been tested for HPAI virus.

FIGURE 1 Sample sites in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Sample sites for the 535 individuals sampled in Latvia, Ukraine, Georgia, the Netherlands, Austria, Germany, Switzerland, Italy, and France. The figure includes previously unpublished samples from January to April 2026.

A weekly compilation of all 33,591 samples (positive and negative; including previously published), collected at each node from August 2024 to April 2026, can be seen in Figure 2. The proportion of positive individuals (bird-level prevalence) per week over the total project period, for all nodes combined, can be seen in Figure 3. Since the beginning of 2026, prevalence has dropped down to a lower level than during the autumn. However, peaks of higher prevalence still occur in some weeks (Figure 3).

TABLE 2 Most recently collected samples in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Total number of collected samples as well as number of samples positive for avian influenza virus. The table includes previously unpublished samples from January to April 2026.

Group/species	Node 2 Latvia			Node 3 Ukraine			Node 4 Georgia			Node 5 Netherlands			Node 6 Austria			Node 6 Germany			Node 6 Switzerland			Node 7 Italy			Node 8 France			Total					
	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI			
<i>Waterfowl</i>																																	
Mute Swan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0
Greylag Goose	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0
Common Shelduck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	45	0	0	0	0	0	45	0	0
Egyptian Goose	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0
Mallard	3	0	0	174	7	0	46	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	17	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	242	8	0
Domestic Mallard	0	0	0	0	0	0	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24	0	0
Northern Pintail	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0
Eurasian Teal	0	0	0	4	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	16	1	0
Garganey	0	0	0	0	0	0	30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30	0	0
Common Pochard	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Tufted Duck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
<i>Grebes</i>																																	
Black-necked Grebe	0	0	0	4	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	0
Great Crested Grebe	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
<i>Cormorants</i>																																	
Great Cormorant	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	47	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	51	0	0
<i>Rails</i>																																	
Eurasian Coot	0	0	0	58	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	58	3	0
<i>Waders</i>																																	
Eurasian Oystercatcher	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0
Ruff	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Red Knot	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Ruddy Turnstone	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Dunlin	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34	0	0
Common Redshank	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0
Common Snipe	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
<i>Larids</i>																																	
Black-headed Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	114	0	0	0	0	0	16	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	142	0	0
Mediterranean Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Yellow-legged Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	72	0	0	0	0	0	72	0	0
Lesser Black-backed Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	54	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	54	10	0
Total	3	0	0	242	11	0	232	0	0	103	10	0	96	0	0	29	1	0	3	0	0	45	0	0	72	0	0	825	22	0			

FIGURE 2 Weekly summary of collected samples in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. In total, 33,591 samples (negative samples in blue; samples positive for avian influenza virus in orange) have been collected at nine nodes between August 2024 and April 2026, yielding 2,334 samples positive for avian influenza virus, including 103 samples positive for HPAI virus. The figures also include samples published in previous reports.

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FIGURE 3 Weekly bird-level prevalence of avian influenza virus in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Weekly prevalence of individuals positive for avian influenza virus from all nodes combined between August 2024 and April 2026, separated for each year. The figures only include bird samples (excluding mussels and water samples). The number of individuals (here: any individual bird sampled on a given day) are included at the top of the figure.

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2.2 GENOMICS SUMMARY

Since the last report was published on 27th of March 2026 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19254891>), and as of the 15th of April 2026, one new H5N1 sequence has been generated from a sample positive for avian influenza virus. This sample was collected in France (Node 8 Camargue Region) in January from a Eurasian Teal.

Genetic analysis of the haemagglutinin (HA) gene sequences from this individual found that it belonged to the H5 clade 2.3.4.4b of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) (Figure 4A).

The H5 HPAI sequence was classified as the DI.2.1 sub-genotype of the EA-2024-DI genotype, according to the European Union Reference Laboratory for Avian Influenza classification system (<https://github.com/izsvenezie-virology/genin2>) and was found to be similar to other DI.2.1 sequences from the SENTINEL Wild Birds project (Figure 4B), as well as elsewhere in Europe.

The Nextstrain builds are available on the SENTINEL Wild Birds Group (<https://nextstrain.org/groups/SentinelWildBirds>).

Aside from the H5 sequence, there have been two non-H5 avian influenza sequences generated from samples collected in Italy (Node 7 Veneto Region). The sequences were generated from samples collected from Eurasian Teal and were found to be of the H1N1 and H9N2 subtypes.

This analysis is based on data obtained from the GISAID EpiFlu platform (Elbe and Buckland-Merrett 2017; Shu and McCauley 2017) up to 21st of April 2026, and is accessible at <https://doi.org/10.55876/gis8.260427tg>. Where sequences were included that are under a publishing embargo at the time of writing, specific permission to utilise these data was obtained from the Data Provider.

A

B

FIGURE 4 Phylogenetic analyses of the H5 HA sequences generated by Node 8 Camargue Region. A. Image of the H5 HA sequences generated by the SENTINEL Wild Birds project, with the 2.3.4.4b and EA-nonGsGd clades highlighted. **B.** Zoom image of the HA tree focusing on the H5 highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) clade 2.3.4.4b sequences from Node 8 Camargue Region in relation to other sequences from Europe and surrounding countries. The new sequence generated in this period is highlighted with an arrow. In **A** and **B**, tip shapes are coloured according to the sampling node.

3. CONCLUSION

During the current reporting period, overall avian influenza virus prevalence remained low (4%), which is considerably lower than levels observed during the autumn and early winter period. However, this overall prevalence was largely driven by detections from a small number of sampling events, with most nodes showing few or no positive cases. This suggests that prevalence was close to zero across most of the study area. This decline is consistent with previously observed seasonal patterns, where prevalence peaks during autumn migration and decreases towards spring. Despite the overall low prevalence, variation among species was evident. The highest prevalence was observed in Lesser Black-backed Gull (19%). However, all individuals of this species were sampled on the same day and at the same location in the Netherlands, indicating that this result likely reflects a localised event rather than a broader species-level pattern. Mallards showed the second highest prevalence (6%), which, given the time of year, represents a relatively elevated level. Notably, 6 of the 8 positive Mallards were sampled on the same day and at the same location in Ukraine, suggesting that this pattern is also partly driven by a localised cluster of infections, although it still supports the continued role of Mallards as key reservoir hosts.

No confirmed cases of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) virus were detected among the samples included in this report. However, three H5-positive samples have not yet been assessed for pathogenicity, meaning that the presence of HPAI virus cannot be entirely excluded. At the broader temporal scale, weekly data indicate that prevalence has declined since the beginning of 2026, following elevated levels during autumn 2025. This likely reflects reduced aggregation of migratory waterfowl and changing ecological conditions during late winter and early spring.

During this period, one H5 sequence has been generated, which was from the 2.3.4.4b HPAI clade and confirmed to be the DI.2.1 sub-genotype, which has predominated in Europe since mid-September 2025 (EFSA 2025). This sequence demonstrated high similarity to sequences collected across Europe, including other sequences generated by the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. In addition to prior reports, this similarity highlights the connectivity between the active and passive sampling schemes that are ongoing within Europe.

Overall, the results show that avian influenza virus prevalence has declined to relatively low levels during late winter and early spring, following the higher prevalence observed during autumn. While no confirmed HPAI cases were detected in the analysed samples, genomic data indicate that HPAI viruses of the 2.3.4.4b clade continue to circulate in Europe. Continued surveillance remains essential to detect changes in prevalence, host use, and viral evolution.

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Node 3: Linnaeus University (Sweden); National Scientific Centre Institute of Experimental and Clinical Veterinary Medicine (Kharkiv, Ukraine); State Research Institute for Laboratory Diagnostics and Veterinary and Sanitary Expertise (Kyiv, Ukraine)

Node 4: Centre of Wildlife Disease Ecology (CWDE), Ilia State University; State Laboratory of Agriculture of Georgia

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Node 7: Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale delle Venezie; Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale (ISPRA)

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